

Virtual Climate Activation: A Framework Approach to Sustainable Food Consumption in Games

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- | We are in the middle of the climate crisis
- | It is actually a polycrisis
- | We need top-down and bottom-up action
- | Games can help

Steinhauser & Vollgruber (2024) based on Ouariachi et al. (2019)

Beecarbonize
Charles Games
2023

Gibbon: Beyond the Trees
Broken Rules
2022

Bear & Breakfast
Gummy Cat
2022

Achievable

Games do not need a dedicated sustainability connection
Normalizing behavior is as important as direct links to the crisis
Message could be even stronger
Behavioral messages should be concrete

Credibility

Expert involvement strengthens message and studio credibility
Naming experts and projects enables inherent player activation
Directly links to call-to-actions, such as donation calls

Concrete

Encyclopedias can provide additional information
But: Should not hide essential gameplay info
Multistep approach: Short teaser, long teaser, longer encyclopedia entry
Important to often highlight the feature and keep barrier low
Low barrier strengthens reward mechanism, which strengthens replayability

Experiential learning

A powerful tool to support other components
Should be actively searched for, as it creates truly unique experiences

Efficacy-enhancing

Mechanisms of game and positive messages should align
Otherwise: ludo-narrative dissonance

- | Expand analysis to wider catalogue of games
- | Focused evaluation of sub-groups of mechanisms or specific examples
- | Impact analysis beyond short-term cognitive changes

| Thank you

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